

Evaluate the maximum stresses and torque produced during power transmission of a height adjustable ceiling chandelier

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Abstract:

We are going to make a chandelier which is connected to motor through pulley

According to given statements, we have to study , analyze the system in accordance to stress strain loadings etc while the system has given the external power transmission.

The main aim is to study the behavior of stresses. A chandelier hanging down with, string has tension in it. It may have some weight which has some normal force. we use the method of force resolution stress analysis to find stresses on it. We have to find torque on it. Complete working process is , we give power through battery to motor ,here is DC gear motor which moves 180 forward and then next interval it moves backward. This will allow it to move upward and downward.

We use three types of material strings to done our stress analysis. Here we use spring, copper coil and stretchable thread. We compare the values how much change is there.

Figure 1 FBD

Introduction:

Chandelier:

The American Heritage Dictionary defines a **chandelier** as "a branched, decorative lighting fixture that holds a number of bulbs or candles and is suspended from a ceiling." In the interest of fire safety, today's chandeliers rarely hold candles, but they still impart an incomparable ambiance.

- Crystal : For elegant style, choose a shimmering crystal chandelier. Its glittering crystals make a dramatic decor statement.
- Glass : Who says your chandelier can't be casual? Use a glass chandelier to create a design focus that's as modern and breezy as you wish.
- Tiffany : A type of glass chandelier, Tiffany fixtures feature stained glass shades in the Art Nouveau fashion of the early 20th century.
- Candle : A candle chandelier is the most traditional variety. Its candle-shaped lightbulbs evoke the original meaning of the word chandelier, French for "candleholder."

DC Gear motor:

A gear motor is an all-in-one combination of a motor and gearbox. The addition of a gear head to a motor reduces the speed while increasing the torque output. The most important parameters in regards to gear motors are speed (rpm), torque (lb-in) and efficiency (%). We are using **100 rpm** motor .

Figure 2 DC motor

Motor driver can be used with this motor that has a voltage of between 5 and 35V DC.

Specifications of our motor.

1. RPM: 100.
2. Operating Voltage: 12V DC
3. Gearbox: Attached Plastic (spur)
4. Gearbox Shaft diameter: 6mm with internal hole
5. Torque: 2 kg-cm
6. No-load current = 60 mA(Max)
7. Load current = 300 mA(Max)

Pulley:

A pulley is a wheel that carries a flexible rope, cord, cable, chain, or belt on its rim. Pulleys are used singly or in combination to transmit energy and motion. Pulleys with grooved rims are called sheaves. What are the 3 types of pulleys?

The following are **the types of pulley**:

- I. Fixed pulley.
- II. Moving Pulley.
- III. Compound Pulley.

We are using fixed pulley.

It is used to lift load with little effort.

Figure 3

pulley

5 Objectives

Aim is to find stress torque during power transmission.

6. Literature Review:

For quantitative understanding of string, it is very important to calculate the stresses at rod of a system, because these calculations help us answer a very important practical parameter i.e. the value of the external load. Further we have to study the power , torque which are acting there .

Among the parameters and tests that have been developed, mostly during the last quarter of the twentieth century, to describe the factor of safety of a material in a quantitative and reproducible manner,

“The ratio of the ultimate strength of a member or piece of material to the actual working stress or the maximum permissible stress when in use.”

Power is calculated by using rotation moment of the motor. Torque is calculated by using power of that DC motor. we may change the material of string to study the factor of safety and also what are the main changes happen there. We find torque factor of safety and power transmission by **following formulas:**

$$\text{Power} = \text{Voltage} * \text{Current}$$

$$\text{Torque} = \text{Power} / (\omega)$$

$$\omega = 2*3.14*N / 60$$

N = RPM number of given motor

$$\text{Safety Factor} = \text{ultimate stress} / \text{Allowable stress}$$

1.1 Stress Concentrations:

We find these values by simple formula of stress.

$$A = \text{Pi} (r^2)$$

$$\sigma = P / A$$

1.2 Safety factor :

$$\text{Safety factor} = \text{ultimate stress} / \text{Allowable stress}$$

Methodology:

First we use the wood to make the base of chandelier and then we make a wooden frame on which the pulley is attached

Then we use motor of 100 rpm to transmit power to move chandelier upward and downward.

Then we use a battery of 12 volts which is connected to the DC motor. It produces current of 1.2ampere.

We calculate the power transmission and torque produce by the mo tor

For making chandelier design we use a metal strip and mold it in circular shape

Then we use metal chains to make it like chandelier.

Then for analysis we first use the nylon thread from which we calculate the stress in the strings when the chandelier moves. We also find the factor of safety for nylon thread.

Then we use copper wire for analysis from which we calculate the stress. We also find the factor of safety for copper.

The factor of safety of copper is much greater than nylon thread But we use the nylon thread in our model because it is inexpensive and the weight of our chandelier is less so it bears it easily.

Calculations :

DC Gear Motor:

$$\text{Power} = ?$$

$$\text{Voltage} = 12 \text{ Volt}$$

$$\text{Motor RPM} = 100$$

$$\text{Current required for motor} = 2.04 \text{ Ampere}$$

$$\text{Power} = \text{Voltage} * \text{Current}$$

$$= 12 * 2.04$$

$$= 24.48 \text{ Watts}$$

Now, finding torque,

$$\text{Torque} = \text{Power} / (\omega)$$

$$\omega = 2 * \pi * N / 60$$

$$\text{torque} = p / (2 * \pi * n / 60)$$

$$= 60 * 24.48 / 2 * 3.14 * 100$$

$$= 2.33 \text{ N.m}$$

We first calculate the forces acting on the system and after this we have to calculate the stress for the system.

$$\text{Area of nylon thread} = \pi * r^2$$

$$\text{Diameter} = 0.0012 \text{ m}$$

$$R = d / 2$$

$$= 0.0012 / 2$$

$$= \mathbf{0.0006 \text{ m}^2}$$

$$A = 3.14 * (0.006)^2$$

$$= 0.00000113$$

$$= \mathbf{1.13 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2}$$

$$\text{Area of copper wire} = \pi * r^2$$

$$D = 2R = 2 * 0.1 \text{ cm} = 2 * 0.1 * 10^{-2} \text{ m}$$

$$= \mathbf{0.002 \text{ m}^2}$$

$$\text{Area} = 3.14 * 0.002$$

$$= \mathbf{0.0062 \text{ m}^2}$$

Forces on this chandelier are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_a &= F (r \cos \theta \mathbf{i} - r \sin \theta \mathbf{j} - 0.30\mathbf{k}) / ((r \cos \theta)^2 + (-r \sin \theta)^2 + (-0.30)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= (0.35 * 9.81) (0.15 \cos 77^\circ \mathbf{i} - 0.15 \sin 77^\circ \mathbf{j} - 0.30 \mathbf{k}) / ((0.15 \cos 77^\circ)^2 + (-0.15 \sin 77^\circ)^2 \\ &\quad + (-0.30)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= \mathbf{(0.548i - 1.45j - 3.11k)N} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_b &= F (-r \cos \theta \mathbf{i} - r \sin \theta \mathbf{j} - 0.30\mathbf{k}) / ((-r \cos \theta)^2 + (-r \sin \theta)^2 + (-0.30)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= (0.35 * 9.81) (-0.15 \cos 77^\circ \mathbf{i} - 0.15 \sin 77^\circ \mathbf{j} - 0.30 \mathbf{k}) / ((-0.15 \cos 77^\circ)^2 + (-0.15 \sin 77^\circ)^2 \\ &\quad + (-0.30)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= \mathbf{(-0.548i - 1.45j - 3.11k)N} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_c &= F (0.15\mathbf{j} - 0.3\mathbf{k}) / (0.15^2 + (-0.3)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= (0.35 * 9.81) (0.15\mathbf{j} - 0.3\mathbf{k}) / (0.15^2 + (-0.3)^2)^{1/2} \\ &= \mathbf{(1.55j - 3.11k)N} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_r = \mathbf{F}_a + \mathbf{F}_b + \mathbf{F}_c$$

$$= \mathbf{(-1.35j - 9.33k)N}$$

$$F = 9.4 \text{ N}$$

We use two different types of material for analysis then after comparing their values and the factor of safety for both of materials.

A) For the Nylon thread stress is:

350 g is the maximum weight it can bear without deforming. Stress concentration on each string is given by:

$$\text{Stress} = F / A$$

Stress of string $F_a = \text{Force} / \text{area of nylon string}$

$$\text{Area of nylon} = 1.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^2$$

$$F_a = 3.474 \text{N}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stress at a} &= 3.474 / 1.13 \times 10^{-6} \\ &= 6 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Stress at string b = Force/Area

$$F_b = 3.474 \text{N}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stress at b} &= 3.474 / 1.13 \times 10^{-6} \\ &= 6 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Stress at string c = Force/ Area

$$F_c = 3.474$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Stress at c} &= 3.474 / 1.13 \times 10^{-6} \\ &= 6 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Safety factor = Ultimate stress / allowable stress

Ultimate stress for nylon thread = 40 MPa

Allowable stress = 18 MPa

$$S.F = 40 \text{ MPa} / 18 \text{ MPa}$$

$$= 2.22$$

For Copper

Forces are same in each rod.

Stress concentration on each string is given by:

$$\text{Stress} = F / A$$

= F of string a , b , c / area of copper string

$$\text{Area of copper} = 0.0062 \text{m}^2$$

$$F_a = 3.474 \text{N}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress at a} &= 3.474 / 0.0062 \\ &= 50.3 \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress at string b} &= \text{Force} / \text{Area} \\ F_b &= 3.474 \text{ N}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress at b} &= 3.474 / 0.0062 \\ &= 50.3 \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress at string c} &= \text{Force} / \text{Area} \\ F_c &= 3.474\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Stress at c} &= 3.474 / 0.0062 \\ &= 50.3 \text{ Pa}\end{aligned}$$

Safety factor = Ultimate stress / allowable stress

Ultimate stress for Copper thread = 210 Mpa

Allowable stress = ?

S.F = 1.3

Because copper wire deforming under load beyond its yield point.

Yield point of copper is 137Mpa

We are setting our allowable stress at 135 Mpa.

$$\text{S.F} = 210 \text{ Mpa} / 135 \text{ Mpa}$$

= 1.5

Comparison Table:

Nylon Thread	Copper Wire
Inexpensive material	Costly
Less durable	Durable
Produces axial Force	Produces axial force

Results and Discussion:

First we calculate the stress of copper wire and the nylon thread which comes out 50 Pa for copper and 6 MPa for nylon thread. Then we find the failure force of nylon thread which is 45.91N which means that it is the maximum force that a material can bear before failure. Ultimate stress tensile for copper is 137 Mpa while for nylon is 40 Mpa .

So we calculate safety factor for both the materials. The safety factor for the nylon is 2.22 and for the copper 1.5 .

Copper has less factor of safety because nylon is weak material. Copper has high specific strength so that's why it has less factor safety ratio.

We use a DC gear motor of rpm 100 which is connected to a battery of 12 volts.

The power transmitted by the motor is 8.16 watts.

The motor produces a torque of 0.78Nm.

The diameter of nylon thread is 0.13cm if we increase the diameter the stress of it decrease. And vice versa.

Application:

Following are the applications:

Rock picking clamp

Figure picking clamp10 rock

Bridges

Figure 11 bridge

3 pole tower

Figure 12 3 pole tower

Conclusion:

We are now able to study the mechanical properties of every material. We have ability to design a project according to our requirements. We are now able to design and set properties according to get desired characteristics.

Future Recommendations

While making a chandelier we should first consider the factor of safety of material and the diameter of strings to which it is attached. The diameter should be appropriate to reduce the tension and stress in the string. It will increase the life span of the material

Work Distribution

we all work together like a team .We do all the task related to project with coordination.

TASK	MEMBER WHO DID
PROTOTYPE	Muaz Ahmed Abdullah Imtinan Faiz Abdul Qudoos Ahmed
PROJECT REPORT AND ANALYSIS AND CALCULATION	Muaz Ahmed Abdullah Imtinan Faiz Abdul Qudoos Ahmed
PRESENATION	Muaz Ahmed Abdullah Imtinan Faiz Abdul Qudoos Ahmed

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